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INFLUENCE OF SEASONS OF THE YEAR AND AGE OF ANIMALS ON NEMATODE INFECTION IN RURAL ANIMALS IN NAKHCHIVAN AUTONOMOUS REPUBLIC

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Abstract. *The article examines the influence of seasonal dynamics and age-related factors on the degree of nematode infection in ruminant animals. It was established that in sheep, the prevalence of invasion during the winter period (December–January) was 19.2%, whereas in the autumn months (October–November) this indicator reached its maximum value of 43.2%. In the subsequent period, a repeated decrease in the level of infection to 18.7% was observed, which is attributed to the impact of unfavorable environmental factors, primarily the absence of optimal temperature conditions necessary for the full development of helminths, their eggs, and larval stages.*

The prevalence of nematode invasion localized in the digestive system of ruminant animals varies significantly depending on age. It was found that with increasing age of the animals, there is a statistically significant decrease in nematode infection rates, which is likely associated with the formation of age-related immunity and adaptive mechanisms of the host organism.

Keywords: *Nematodes 1, ruminant animals 2, helminth 4, parasite 5.*

Аннотация. *В статье исследовано влияние сезонной динамики и возрастного фактора на степень заражённости жвачных животных нематодами. Установлено, что у овец в зимний период (декабрь–январь) экстенсивность инвазии составляла 19,2%, в то время как в осенние месяцы (октябрь–ноябрь) данный показатель достигал максимального значения — 43,2%. В последующий период отмечалось повторное снижение уровня заражённости до 18,7%, что обусловлено воздействием неблагоприятных экологических факторов, прежде всего отсутствием оптимальных температурных условий, необходимых для полноценного развития гельминтов, их яиц и личиночных стадий.*

Экстенсивность нематодной инвазии, локализованной в пищеварительной системе жвачных животных, достоверно варьирует в зависимости от возраста. Установлено, что с увеличением возраста животных наблюдается статистически значимое снижение показателей заражённости нематодами, что, вероятно, связано с формированием возрастного иммунитета и адаптационных механизмов организма хозяина.

Materials and methods of the study

Helminthological materials were collected in accordance with generally accepted parasitological methods and studied in laboratory conditions. During the study, complete helminthological dissection, compressor and coprological methods were applied. The internal organs of animals slaughtered by the complete helminthological dissection method were sequentially examined and the presence of helminths was determined. During the compressor method, the diaphragm and some intermediate hosts were squeezed between two glasses, and the larval stages of helminths were detected. Within the framework of coprological studies, feces samples collected from different areas were analyzed by helminth ovoscopy based on the Berman, Fulliborn and Visniauskas methods, which are distinguished by their high efficiency in the diagnosis of gastrointestinal strongylides.

Discussion and results of the study

Animal husbandry is one of the important sectors of the national and agricultural economy in the Republic of Azerbaijan and its integral part, the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. Parasitism of nematodes (roundworms) in ruminant animals leads to a decrease in meat, milk, skin and wool productivity, as well as death. Treatment of gastrointestinal nematodes, which are mainly chronic parasites, is economically unprofitable.

The list of human parasitic worms includes more than 400 species of helminths. Of these, 207 species belong to the type of flatworms - Platyhelminthes (trematodes - 141 species, cestodes - 63 species) and 145 species of roundworms - Nemathelminthes [1, 2, 4].

The study of the impact of natural phenomena and seasonal changes on the spread of helminths and the formation of nematode fauna is of both theoretical and practical importance. The study of the seasonal periodicity of nematode infection of ruminants, on the one hand, allows us to determine the biology and ecological characteristics of nematodes, their seasonal interactions with their hosts, and on the other hand, the seasons in which animals are infected with nematodes with higher extensiveness and dangerous periods.

The seasonal change of environmental factors has a serious impact on the formation of the nematode fauna of animals. Seasonal variability affects both the helminth itself and various stages of development outside the animal body.

Therefore, taking into account the impact of seasonal changes on the spread of nematodes, we studied the seasonal infection of ruminants with nematodes and obtained certain regularities [3, 5].

Infection of sheep with nematodes was noted with high extensiveness and intensity in all seasons of the year.

For this purpose, 125 sheep (32 in spring, 31 in summer, 31 in autumn, 31 in winter) were studied by us. The total infection of animals with helminths was 32.3% in spring, 34.1% in summer, 18.7% in autumn, and 12.4% in winter, respectively.

Chart 1.

SEASONAL NEMATODE INFECTION OF SHEEP

The infection of ruminant animals with nematodes is characterized by a single-peak curve. Thus, in sheep, starting from 19.2% in winter - December, January, to the peak point - 43.2% in autumn - October, November, then again due to the influence of environmental factors (due to the lack of optimal temperature necessary for the development of the helminth, its eggs and larvae), the infection decreased to 18.7%.

Since nematodes are geohelminths, their development and spread depend on the influence of abiotic factors of the environment. The eggs of geohelminths retain their viability in the soil for up to 17 months. Since the soil has the necessary moisture and humidity for the development of eggs, the eggs become invasive and remain in the soil, causing infection of animals at all seasons of the year [6].

Thus, during the studies conducted by season, a certain regularity was obtained: the detected nematodes were highly prevalent in the gastrointestinal tract of ruminants in spring, autumn, and winter, and relatively low in summer.

The studies determined how age affects the infection of ruminants with parasitic nematodes. The formation of nematode fauna in the gastrointestinal tract of ruminants is reflected in the graph below (Chart 2).

As can be seen from the graph, the extensiveness of nematodes parasitic in the digestive system of ruminants varies depending on age. Thus, as the age of animals increases, the extensiveness of their infection with nematodes decreases.

Detection of helminth infection in animals depending on their age is of practical importance. Thus, by knowing the age dynamics of helminth infection in animals, by predicting in advance at what age period the infection can infect humans and ruminant domestic animals, it is possible to prevent helminth infection in humans and animals with preventive measures.

Conclusion

During the study, it was determined that the extensiveness of nematodes parasitic in the digestive system of ruminants varies depending on age. Thus, as the age of the animals increases, the extensiveness of their infection with nematodes decreases.

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